

Beyond Traditional Models: Assessing SME Sustainability in Thailand's Food Processing Sector Through Agility and Innovation Dimensions

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Abstract

Background: Economic growth, food processing, security, and rural employment are all significantly influenced by small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Thailand's food processing industry. These SMEs are subject to strict regulations and resource limitations.

Objective: The study aims to examine the influence of two core capabilities on SME sustainability in Thailand's food processing industry: (1) organisational agility, operationalised through the dimensions of flexibility, adaptability, and resilience, and (2) organisational innovation, measured through the dimensions of leadership and people.

Methodology: This study employed a quantitative, descriptive survey design. Data was collected via a structured questionnaire from a sample of 250 executives and business owners in Thailand's processed food industry. The hypothesised model was tested using Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) in SmartPLS 4.0.

Results: The results reveal that both organisational agility (notably through its dimensions of adaptability, flexibility and resilience) and organisational innovation (through leadership and people) have significant and positive effects on SMEs' sustainability. All five dimensions were found to be statistically significant predictors.

Conclusion: This study confirms the significant role of organisational agility and organisational innovation as key drivers of SME sustainability. The research provides a valuable reference for future studies by validating adapted scales for these constructs, which are tailored to the unique economic and social context of the food processing industry in Thailand.

Unique Contribution: This study is beneficial in theory and practice for measuring organisations' agility and innovation to assess the sustainability of small and medium-sized businesses. It contributes to the theoretical and methodological discussion by incorporating governance into classic models (economic, social, and environmental).

Key Recommendation: Based on the above results, the author proposes six policy recommendations to enhance the organisational agility and innovation of small and medium enterprises within the context of development and integration in Thailand's food processing industry. To capitalise on this opportunity, it is essential to implement the aforementioned solutions simultaneously to eliminate institutional bottlenecks and enhance the sustainability of SME in Thailand.

Keywords: Sustainability assessment, Organisational agility, Organisational innovation, SME sustainability, Food processing industry, Thailand

Introduction

In the VUCA world of rapid, unexpected shifts, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) must develop internal capabilities for speed, adaptability, and flexibility to remain competitive and resilient. Furthermore, maintaining technological leadership, global market presence, and understanding customer behaviour requires operational efficiency, strategic insight, and innovation. In such situations, the ability to proactively adapt to change has become a strategic imperative for long-term survival and value creation.

Numerous studies have explored the dynamic capabilities that underlie firm adaptability, particularly the relationship between organisational agility (OA) and organisational innovation (OI) in the context of organisational sustainability (OS). Agility, as conceptualised by the Iacocca Institute (Yusuf et al., 1999), encompasses the capacity to sense change and reconfigure resources accordingly. Innovation, in turn, builds upon leadership engagement and employee creativity to implement new ideas and improve performance (Lasrado, 2019). Collectively, organisational agility and organisational innovation form the strategic foundations that enable organisations to navigate disruptions and pursue sustainability (Mengistu & Panizzolo, 2023; Teece et al., 1997).

Thailand's food processing industry plays a crucial role in national food security, exports, and rural employment. According to the report, SMEs continue to face persistent limitations in adaptability and innovation. Although the economy has been significant, companies face competence constraints, fragmented innovation systems, and regulatory compliance challenges. Moreover, Somwethee et al. (2023) found that Thai community companies lack innovation and adaptability, hindering their sustainability. These structural deficiencies increase vulnerability to external factors and compromise their ability to align with ESG and SDGs.

Numerous studies have recognised the significance of agility and innovation; however, their precise definitions vary. To address this, integrated frameworks are proposed and tested in practice in this study. Specifically, we operationalise organisational agility as a higher-order construct comprising three critical dimensions: adaptability, resilience, and flexibility. Moreover, organisational innovation is driven by leadership and people. This framework fills a research gap by providing a detailed assessment of how these separate yet interrelated elements contribute to SMEs' sustainability in Thailand's food processing industry.

Theoretical review and hypothesis development

Underlying theory

Strategic meta-capability organisational agility (OA) involves quick resource reconfiguration, continuous learning, and proactive adaptation (Teece et al. 1997; Barlette & Baillette, 2022). Flexible, adaptable, and resilient OA helps organisations survive unforeseen environments. Repurposing operational, human, financial, and supply chain resources provides flexibility (Settembre-Blundo et al., 2021). Lu and Ramamurthy (2011) define adaptability as the firm's ability to institutionalise learning and procedural change in response to external changes. Resilience is the ability to remain stable, recover, and achieve long-term goals. These characteristics make agility a vital higher-order theoretical construct for uncertain SMEs.

In contrast, organisational innovation (OI) captures the ability to generate and diffuse new ideas and practices that renew competitiveness (Lasrado, 2019). In small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), organisational intelligence (OI) is assessed through leadership and personnel. Leadership embeds an innovation culture through senior management's vision, communication, and resource mobilisation (Jeong et al. 2020; Srisathan et al., 2023). Employee participation, creativity, and training stimulate bottom-up innovation (Sarango-Lalangui et al. 2023; Hossain et al., 2025). OA detects and responds to environmental change, while OI turns responsiveness into outcomes, making them complementary but separate strategic capacities.

Most models examine agility and innovation independently. Although Mengistu and Panizzolo (2023) address economic, environmental, social, and governance challenges, they do not explain how OA and OI interact in sector-specific sustainability situations. Thus, SMEs in emerging economies, such as Thailand's food-processing industry, struggle with traceability, regulatory compliance, and ESG alignment (Somwethee et al., 2023).

Organisational Sustainability in SMEs

Sustainable business practices are essential for SMEs, especially in resource-intensive industries like food processing. According to Mengistu and Panizzolo (2022), they present an economic, environmental, and social framework. Cost efficiency, profitability, and market competitiveness are key to economic sustainability; energy consumption and ecological responsibility are essential for environmental sustainability; and employee well-being, customer satisfaction, and community engagement are crucial for social sustainability. Recent research confirms the necessity for multidimensional frameworks. Somwethee et al. (2023) found that leadership-driven and structural flexibility were essential for community companies in Thailand to survive a complex situation.

Building on this foundation, the current study introduces a fourth-dimensional governance approach to address growing demands for transparency, stakeholder obligations, and ethical management. Traceability, regulatory compliance, and safety certifications are crucial for long-term credibility in Thailand's processed food SMEs.

In this study, the researcher defines organizational sustainability in SMEs as the outcome of organizational operations utilizing resources to achieve results in terms of economic (e.g., financial

return, market competitiveness), social (e.g., employee satisfaction, customer trust, community impact), environmental (e.g., energy and material use), and governance (e.g., participation, integrity, transparency, accountability) factors. Thus, this study enables a context-sensitive evaluation of sustainability in Thai SMEs, bridging internal capability development with external alignment of SDGs and ESG.

Organizational Agility

In the early 1990s, the Iacocca Institute concept of organisational agility explained a firm's ability to survive in VUCA scenarios (Yusuf et al., 1999). Agility is characterised by reactivity, speed, adaptability, and expertise in response to globalisation and the compression of product life cycles. Over the past few studies, the concept has evolved into a strategic meta-capability involving rapid resource reconfiguration, continuous learning, and proactive adaptation (Barlette & Baillette, 2022; Teece et al., 1997). According to Somwethee et al. (2023), leadership-driven agility and learning-based impartiality impact the sustainability of Thai SMEs. Thus, flexibility has become a strategic driver, particularly in volatile industries such as the processed food sector.

Organisational agility (OA) refers to an organisation's ability to recognise environmental changes, respond effectively, and adjust its internal structures to remain competitive. It encompasses both operational responsiveness and strategic foresight. Agility helps SME respond to regulatory changes, resource restrictions, and market volatility. Agility, particularly proactive learning, cross-functional adaptation, and leadership alignment, sustains performance under uncertainty (Nguyen et al., 2024). These findings suggest that emerging markets need OA to navigate change and build sustainable routes. This study operationalises organisational agility in three dimensions:

Flexibility (X1)

Organisational agility, especially in SMEs with resource limitations and market unpredictability, relies on flexibility. It refers to the organisation's ability to rapidly reconfigure its internal structures in response to both internal disruptions and external volatility, including changes in operations, human capital deployment, financial controls, information flows, and supply chain networks (Settembre-Blundo et al., 2021). A critical distinction in the literature is the relationship between flexibility and the broader concept of agility. While some scholars use the terms interchangeably, Walter (2021) offers a more nuanced view. Some scholars confuse flexibility with agility, whereas others view it as an operational rather than a strategic or integrative capability. Flexibility can be operational (e.g., changing product lines or delivery schedules), human capital (multiskilling), information (IT-based realignment), or financial (adaptive budgeting and cash flow reorganising).

Agility is a higher-order, strategic capability for navigating volatile environments, whereas flexibility is a foundational, operational enabler that enables the rapid reconfiguration of resources. For instance, treat flexibility as a component that contributes to overall resilience and agility. This distinction is critical for our study: by measuring flexibility, we are not measuring agility in its entirety, but instead capturing a core, measurable operational capacity that underpins Thai SMEs' ability to be truly agile. This theoretical positioning justifies our hypothesis that enhancing operational flexibility is a direct pathway to improving organisational sustainability.

Recent research highlights the need for flexibility for SME sustainability. According to Somwethee et al. (2023), leadership-driven responsiveness and structural flexibility in Thai community enterprises enable them to endure external pressures and survive. Thus, this suggests that flexibility is a proactive enabler of sustained performance, especially in food-processing SMEs in Thailand, which face regulatory uncertainty, supply chain disruptions, and shifts in customer behaviour. Therefore, the following hypotheses are proposed.

H1: Flexibility, as a dimension of organisational agility, has a significant positive impact on SMEs' sustainability in Thailand's food processing industry.

Adaptability (X2)

A firm's ability to learn, evolve, and adjust its operating procedures in response to changing environmental requirements is called adaptability. The actions Theory of the firm and strategic contingency theory explain this concept, which is helpful for businesses in distributing resources, studying, and managing change. However, resource restrictions make institutionalising adaptation challenging for SMEs. Thus, SMEs that develop structured learning systems, continually renew them, and codify change processes perform better in dynamic environments (Teece et al., 1997). The processed food sector in Thailand must adapt quickly to shifting consumer demands, evolving safety regulations, and evolving export standards.

Recent research in community enterprises, as reported by Somwethee et al. (2023), found that adaptive leadership, opportunity recognition, and change readiness improved sustainability. Thus, the findings demonstrate that adaptation is fundamental to the survival of SMEs as a strategic ability for change. Therefore, the following hypotheses are proposed.

H2: Adaptability, as a dimension of organisational agility, has a significant positive impact on SMEs' sustainability in Thailand's food processing industry.

Resilience (X3)

An organisation's resilience is its ability to overcome adversity, recover from disruption, and pursue long-term goals without compromising its fundamental activities. Instead of adaptation, resilience emphasises stability during crises, leveraging leadership, culture, networks, and change readiness (Ciasullo et al., 2024; Gorondutse et al., 2021). However, SMEs' vulnerability to external shocks and limited financial resources make resilience vital. For strategic continuity, flexibility requires trust-based partnerships, diversified leadership, and a proactive approach to crisis management. In the processed food industry, resilience is crucial for navigating perishability, ensuring food safety, and mitigating supply chain threats.

Recently, some scholars. According to Somwethee et al. (2023), Thai community enterprises with resilient leadership and stakeholder participation were better equipped for surviving crises. Structured collaborative creative approaches boost resilience, studies reveal. However, Vasi et al. (2024) found that resilient leadership and external collaborations facilitate the recovery of SMEs from exogenous shocks. Thus, resilience is a strategic capacity for continuity and regenerative transformation, not just a defensive trait. Therefore, the following hypotheses are proposed.

H3: Resilience, as a dimension of organisational agility, has a significant positive impact on the sustainability of SMEs in Thailand's food processing industry.

Organizational Innovation

Organisational innovation has emerged as a strategic enabler of firm competitiveness and adaptability in rapidly evolving environments. It involves the formation, acceptance, and implementation of new ideas, practices, or technologies that enhance organisational processes or outcomes. While innovation in large firms is traditionally associated with R&D investment, in SMEs it is often demonstrated through leadership initiative, collaborative problem-solving, and people-driven processes. In dynamic sectors such as processed food, where product lifecycles are short and compliance objectives are high, innovation becomes necessary not only for growth but for survival. Research in the open innovation domain underlines that innovation capabilities—when embedded at both managerial and employee levels—directly contribute to firm sustainability. (Lasrado, 2019).

Organisational innovation (OI) refers to the firm's internal capacity to transform knowledge into value through novel ideas, structures, and actions. It highlights both top-down vision and bottom-up initiative. In SMEs, where formal R&D roles are rare, innovation often emerges through leadership commitment, trust-based relationships, cross-functional communication, and employee empowerment. These components combine firms to reconfigure routes, experiment under uncertainty, and align with changing stakeholder expectations. Nguyen et al., (2024). In emerging-market SMEs, where resource asymmetry is common, innovation capacity must be both flexible and embedded in human systems. In this study, organisational innovation is operationalised through two core dimensions:

Leadership (X4)

Leadership is a critical enabler of organisational innovation, especially in SMEs where resources are limited and visionary guidance is essential. Lasrado (2019) identifies four key dimensions of innovation-oriented leadership: leadership responsibility, communication and network systems, relationship co-creation, and capability mobilisation. Leadership guarantees foster a culture that legitimises testing and cross-functional cooperation through the active involvement of top management.

Effective communication and networks—both internal and external—facilitate knowledge sharing, idea generation, and collaborative innovation. Relationship co-creation fosters trust between managers and employees, embedding innovation into daily organisational processes. Resource mobilisation ensures critical support (human, financial, and technological) to activate innovation initiatives.

Recent evidence supports the study by Jeong et al. (2020), which found that captaincy commitment to open innovation, coupled with cross-sector cooperation, significantly developed innovation output and sustainability performance in Korean food-processing SMEs. In this context, SME leaders often perform dual roles, making these leadership competencies crucial. Thus, strategic visioning and innovation orchestration are especially vital to sustaining innovation and performance. Therefore, the following hypotheses are proposed.

H4: Leadership, as a dimension of organisational innovation, has a significant positive impact on SMEs' sustainability in Thailand's food processing industry.

People (X5)

In SMEs, where formal R&D structures are often absent, people-driven innovation becomes a cornerstone of competitiveness. Lasrado (2019) identifies three key dimensions of people in innovation: desire to participate, collective imagination, and expertise and training. A culture that encourages employee involvement fosters bottom-up innovation, especially for SMEs with limited scalability.

Collective imagination, determined as collaborative, creative problem-solving, enhances perception and design thinking through cognitive diversity and open dialogue. Moreover, training that improves both technical and interpersonal skills sets up long-term effectiveness and adaptability in innovation. These people-centric capacities are important in processed food SMEs, where consumer preferences develop rapidly, and compliance demands are high.

Empirical evidence reinforces this perspective. According to Sarango-Lalangui et al. (2023), SMEs that foster employee-led ideation and team-based experimentation achieve higher sustainability outputs. Likewise, Hossain et al. (2025) emphasised that employees' participation and innovation culture were critical predictors of green innovation in SMEs. Empowering employees, therefore, the HR function is not a strategic pathway toward sustainability. People form the human infrastructure that sustains innovation ecosystems in resource-constrained environments. Therefore, the following hypotheses are proposed.

H5: People, as a dimension of organisational innovation, have a significant positive impact on SMEs' sustainability in Thailand's food processing industry.

Based on the discussion above, a conceptual framework has been developed for this study, as illustrated in Figure 1. The framework encompasses organisational agility, organisational innovation, and SMEs' Sustainability. Organisational agility and innovation are treated as the independent variables, while SMEs' Sustainability is treated as the dependent variable. The framework considers the relationship between organisational agility, organisational innovation, and organisational sustainability in SMEs.

Source: The author proposed

Figure 1: Proposed conceptual framework linking organisational agility, innovation, and SMEs' sustainability in Thailand's food processing.

Research Methodology

Sample and Data Collection

In this study, the target population comprised small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Thailand's food processing industry. A total of 3,808 food processing SMEs were identified. Therefore, the sample size in this study was determined using the method proposed by Hair et al. (2019), ensuring a representative sample of the study population. Corporate executives served as representatives and cooperated in completing the survey, resulting in 250 questionnaires collected from January 2025 to April 2025. Table 1 presents the profile of characteristics of SMEs in Thailand's food processing industry.

A non-probability quota sampling method was applied to SME classifications, followed by the DBD processed food categories. The sample was evenly split between meat processing and preservation, fish and aquatic animal processing, and fruit and vegetable processing. The pilot tests, involving 30 participants, assessed the instrument's internal consistency. Cronbach's alpha was 0.70, indicating full-scale deployment reliability.

Instrument

The study employed a questionnaire as the survey, which was developed based on a literature review and three experts in the field. The questionnaire's consistency index was determined using the Index of Item Objective Congruence (IOC), yielding a value of 0.95.

Part 1: 35 items measure organizational agility across three dimensions including flexibility (18 items), adaptability (9 items), and resilience (8 items), adapted from Barlette and Baillette (2022), Settembre-Blundo et al. (2021), Lu and Ramamurthy (2011), Part 2: 22 items measure organizational innovation across two dimensions including leadership (11 items) and people (11 items), adapted from Lasrado (2019).

Part 3: 11 items measure SMEs' sustainability across four dimensions, including economic (2 items), social (3 items), environmental (2 items), and governance (4 items), adapted from Mengistu and Panizzolo (2022). Part 4: Captured firm demographic information, including position, years of operation, company size, average annual revenue, and type of processed food industry.

The questionnaire in parts 1–3 used a 5-point Likert Scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The instrument's quality was rigorously assessed in two stages. First, a pilot test with 30 participants from the target population was conducted. The internal consistency for the overall instrument in this pilot phase yielded a Cronbach's alpha of 0.70, which met the minimum threshold for acceptable reliability, confirming the instrument was suitable for full-scale deployment. Subsequently, the reliability for the final dataset (n=250) was re-evaluated. The analysis yielded a more robust overall Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient of 0.827, indicating strong internal consistency for the instrument in the main study, with detailed reliability metrics for each construct presented in Table 2.

Data analysis

Structural equation modelling (SEM) was employed to test the hypotheses, as deemed necessary, appropriate, and effective for confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and model testing, using SmartPLS 4.0 software (Hair et al., 2019). The evaluation procedure (Hair et al., 2017), which

incorporated measurement and structural models, was employed. The measurement model was constructed using CFA to examine the underlying structure, the factors' reliability, and validity. Further, a bootstrapping of 5,000 subsamples was conducted to determine whether the path coefficients were statistically significant using SmartPLS 4.0. As a specialised application of SEM, CFA prioritises evaluating the overall model fit between the observed covariance matrix and the hypothesised structural relationships. Key assumptions underlying CFA include multivariate normality of data, adequate sample size, reflective measurement models and a robust theoretical foundation for the proposed model. SEM is a sophisticated multivariate statistical technique that investigates complex theoretical models by integrating regression and factor analysis elements.

Table 1 Profile of respondents and characteristics of SMEs in Thailand's processed food industry

Measure	Frequency (n=250)	Percentage
<i>Position</i>		
Business owner and executive	64	25.60
Department-level manager	57	22.80
Business partner and executive	46	18.40
Top-level executive (CEO/Managing Director)	36	14.40
Sustainability and environmental officers	19	7.60
Strategic planning officers	15	6.00
Innovation management officers	13	5.20
<i>Years in Operation</i>		
1 – 5 years	46	18.40
6 – 10 years	56	22.40
11 – 15 years	59	23.60
16 – 20 years	66	26.40
More than 20 years	23	9.20
<i>Number of employees</i>		
1 – 5 people	29	11.60
6 – 50 people	61	24.40
51 – 200 people	160	64.00
<i>Average annual revenue</i>		
Less than 1,800,000 Baht per year	67	26.80
1,800,001 – 50,000,000 Baht per year	124	49.60
50,000,001 – 300,000,000 Baht per year	57	22.80
More than 300,000,000 Baht per year	2	0.80
<i>Type of processed food industry</i>		
Meat processing and preservation	84	33.60
Fish and seafood processing and preservation	82	32.80
Fruit and vegetable processing and preservation	84	33.60

Source: Data processed from SPSS 29.0.2

Results

Demographic and descriptive statistics

The study population comprised 250 small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Thailand's food processing industry, as indicated in Table 1. Of all respondents, 25.60% were business owners and executives, and 26.40% had been in operation for 16 to 22 years. The number of employees ranged from 51 to 200, representing 64% of the sample. The majority (49.60%) had an average annual revenue of 1,800,001–50,000,000 Baht. The types of processed food industry were meat processing and preservation, as well as fruit and vegetable processing and preservation (33.60%), followed by fish and seafood processing and preservation (32.80%).

Measurement model

The conceptual framework for this study comprised five reflective constructs: flexibility (X1), adaptability (X2), resilience (X3), leadership (X4), people (X5), and SMEs sustainability (Y). As presented comprehensively in Table 2, all item loadings exceeded the recommended threshold of 0.7, all composite reliability (CR) and Cronbach's alpha values were well above 0.7 (Ali et al., 2018), and the average variance extracted (AVE) for every construct was greater than 0.5. These results provide robust empirical support for the reliability and convergent validity of all six constructs used in this study, in line with the criteria established by (Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Hair et al., 2017). Hair et al. (2017). The discriminant validity assessed the distinctive characteristics of each concept in the structural model. Discriminant validity is confirmed when the square root of each construct's AVE is higher than its correlation with other related variables. While every square root of AVE is higher than the correlation values in the column and row, discriminant validity has been established (See Table 3).

Table 2: Confirmatory factor analysis

	Factor loading	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Flexibility (X1)		0.978	0.978	0.980	0.741
OPERF1	0.880				
OPERF2	0.885				
OPERF3	0.886				
OPERF4	0.875				
OPERF5	0.895				
HUMANF1	0.882				
HUMANF2	0.879				
HUMANF3	0.893				
INFORF1	0.909				
INFORF2	0.898				
INFORF3	0.899				
SCF1	0.903				
SCF2	0.896				
SCF3	0.900				
SCF4	0.909				
FINANF1	0.907				
FINANF2	0.930				
FINANF3	0.906				
Adaptability (X2)		0.958	0.958	0.964	0.747
RESOURCE1	0.912				
RESOURCE2	0.888				
RESOURCE3	0.908				
OL1	0.906				
OL2	0.875				
OL3	0.907				
CMC1	0.897				
CMC2	0.891				
CMC3	0.882				
Resilience (X3)		0.955	0.955	0.962	0.761
LC1	0.907				
LC2	0.920				
LC3	0.903				
NERWORK1	0.904				
NERWORK2	0.900				
NERWORK3	0.893				
CHAGER1	0.926				
CHAGER2	0.928				
Leadership (X4)		0.965	0.965	0.969	0.742
LCS1	0.902				

Table 2: Confirmatory factor analysis

	Factor loading	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
LCS2	0.888				
LCS3	0.884				
LCS4	0.872				
COM1	0.918				
COM2	0.900				
COM3	0.897				
RELA1	0.936				
RELA2	0.929				
RESOURCES1	0.917				
RESOURCES2	0.921				
People (X5)		0.965	0.965	0.969	0.740
PAR1	0.900				
PAR2	0.888				
PAR3	0.900				
CI1	0.914				
CI2	0.905				
CI3	0.869				
TRAIN1	0.903				
TRAIN2	0.888				
TRAIN3	0.906				
MOTIVA1	0.930				
MOTIVA2	0.928				
Organizational Sustainability (Y)		0.987	0.988	0.989	0.888
T_FINGROETH	0.939				
T_MARKETCOMPET	0.924				
T_CUSTOMER	0.946				
T_EMPLOYEE	0.956				
T_COMMUNITY	0.954				
T_ENERGY	0.960				
T_MATERIALS	0.925				
T_PARTICIPATION	0.944				
T_ACCURACY	0.947				
T_TRANSPARENCY	0.921				
T_RESPON	0.952				

Source: Data processed from SmartPLS 4.0

Table 3: Discriminant validity

	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	Y
1. Flexibility (X1)	0.862					

Table 3: Discriminant validity

	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	Y
2. Adaptability (X2)	0.968	1				
3. Resilience (X3)	0.974	0.962	1			
4. Leadership (X4)	0.976	0.960	0.963	1		
5. People (X5)	0.976	0.963	0.961	0.967	1	
6. Sustainability (Y)	0.985	0.980	0.978	0.976	0.978	0.943

Source: Data processed from SmartPLS 4.0

Structural model assessment

The structural model yielded model fit indices from structural path analysis, which was analysed using SmartPLS 4.0. The model demonstrated strong goodness-of-fit, with an R-squared (R^2) of 0.985, indicating that the framework explains 98.5% of the variance in SMEs' sustainability. The model fit was also confirmed by a low Standardised Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) of 0.034, well below the 0.08 threshold. The hypothesis testing supported the relationship between the three dimensions of organisational agility. The dimensions, namely flexibility (X1), adaptability (X2), and resilience (X3), have a significant positive impact on SMEs' sustainability in Thailand's food processing industry. Moreover, the two dimensions of organisational innovation, including leadership (X4) and people (X5), have a significant and positive impact on SMEs' sustainability in Thailand's food processing industry. Thus, Table 4 presents the results of the structural model analysis, delineating the relationships between various constructs and their impact on SMEs' sustainability. The report includes the beta coefficient (β), t-value, and p-value for each path.

Regarding the hypothesised relationships, flexibility (X1) as a dimension of organisational agility significantly positively impacts SMEs' sustainability in Thailand's food processing industry ($\beta = 0.220$, $t = 3.313$, $p < 0.01$). This indicated that an increase in organisational flexibility, or greater organisational agility, was associated with higher levels of organisational sustainability, thereby supporting H1. This result supported H2. Adaptability (X2) as a dimension of organisational agility has a significant positive impact on SMEs' sustainability in Thailand's food processing industry ($\beta = 0.291$, $t = 7.006$, $p < 0.001$). This finding suggests that resilience (X3), as a dimension of organisational agility, has a significant positive impact on SMEs' sustainability in Thailand's food processing industry, thereby supporting H3 ($\beta = 0.202$, $t = 4.286$, $p < 0.01$). Moreover, this result supported H4. Leadership (X4) in organisational innovation has a significantly positive impact on SMEs' sustainability in Thailand's food processing industry ($\beta = 0.154$, $t = 2.961$, $p < 0.01$). Finally, People (X5) organisational innovation has a significantly positive impact on SMEs' sustainability in Thailand's food processing industry ($\beta = 0.139$, $t = 3.517$, $p < 0.01$). This suggested that people involved in organisational innovation were consistently associated with significantly higher SME sustainability, thereby supporting H5.

Table 4: Structural model results

Hypothesized Path	Hypothesis	Beta (β)	Standard Deviation (SD)	t-value	p-value	Decision
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Flexibility (X1) -> Sustainability	H1	0.220	0.067	3.313	0.001	Supported
Adaptability (X2) -> Sustainability	H2	0.291	0.042	7.006	0.000	Supported
Resilience (X3) -> Sustainability	H3	0.202	0.047	4.286	0.000	Supported
Leadership (X4) -> Sustainability	H4	0.154	0.052	2.961	0.003	Supported
People (X5) -> Sustainability	H5	0.139	0.039	3.517	0.000	Supported

Source: Data processed from SmartPLS 4.0

Discussion

The results of this study demonstrate that organisational agility and organisational innovation are crucial for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Thailand's food processing industry. This study finds that organisational agility (OA) positively impacts sustainability in Thailand's food processing industry. All three aspects of adaptability ($\beta = 0.291$), flexibility ($\beta = 0.220$), and resilience ($\beta = 0.202$) were found to have a statistically significant impact on SMEs' sustainability. Therefore, this supports hypotheses H1 to H3. According to Yusuf et al. (1999), they were the first to discuss agility as a means for organisations to address global competitiveness and shorter product life cycles. They focused on important traits, including speed, reactivity, flexibility, and cross-functional knowledge. This idea has grown into a strategic meta-capability and productivity that includes rapidly changing resources, continuous learning, and adaptability (Teece et al., 1997; Barlette & Baillette, 2022). These findings align with previous studies (Gligor et al., 2015), which emphasise that agility enables SMEs to manage volatility and maintain competitiveness, especially in industries facing strict compliance requirements and high supply uncertainty. Therefore, the results provide empirical support for the view that agility is not simply a reactive mechanism but a critical facilitator of long-term sustainability in an unstable environment.

The research results support hypotheses (H4–H5) and show that organisational innovation (OI) has a significant positive effect on sustainability in both the leadership ($\beta = 0.154$) and people ($\beta = 0.139$) dimensions. Innovation remains a vital component of dynamic organisational performance and creativity, even though its effect size is smaller than that of agility. Previous empirical studies also confirm this result, that the framework of Lasrado (2019), which conceptualises innovation through leadership commitment, cross-functional communication, resource mobilisation, and employee participation. In the SME context, where formal R&D structures are limited, people-driven innovation and research to develop new products within limited resources become necessary to sustain ambition and sustainability. Moreover, these results align with the suggestion that innovation-oriented leadership and inclusive workplace cultures enhance flexibility and promote long-term value creation and innovation. Furthermore, insights from Somwethee et al. (2023) highlight how modernisation ecosystems and

cooperation with capabilities promote sustainability in SMEs across various sectors, including digital platform-based enterprises. This confirms the author's expectation and many international empirical studies that a fourth-dimensional governance approach is needed to address growing demands for transparency, stakeholder obligations, and ethical management. Traceability, regulatory compliance, and safety certifications are crucial for long-term credibility in Thailand's processed food SMEs.

In this study, SMEs' sustainability was visualised and measured across four key dimensions: economic, social, environmental, and governance. The important thing is that the coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.985$) indicates that the integrated model, which features both agility and innovation, explains nearly all the variance in SMEs' sustainability outcomes. This confirms the author's expectation and many international empirical studies that a fourth-dimensional governance approach is needed to address growing demands for transparency, stakeholder obligations, and ethical management. Traceability, regulatory compliance, and safety certifications are crucial for long-term credibility in Thailand's food processing sector.

Consequently, the research results are also strengthened by the argument that SMEs' sustainability requires more than practical efficiency; it demands capability-driven frameworks and productivity that enhance strategic agility through an updated innovation organisation. Therefore, combining agility's responsiveness with innovation's transformative power and a reliable system, SMEs in Thailand's food processing industries can better align with ESG goals, control standards, and adapt to shifting consumer expectations and demands. This research thus contributes to the theoretical advancement of SMEs' sustainability policy by authenticating Thailand's food processing industries' capability-based approach for emerging markets.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Organisational agility (OA) and organisational innovation (OI) are crucial for the growth of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Organisational agility and organisational innovation demonstrate their synergistic capabilities, enabling long-term sustainability in dynamic, regulated food processing and planning systems and enhancing refined products in line with client preferences and feedback. Descriptive statistical tools were used to measure the structural equation models of 250 organisations. This study identified the factors and evaluated their impact on the sustainability of SMEs in the Thai food processing industry. The study identified five factors that impact SME sustainability. Thus, the author provides policy recommendations for SMEs' sustainability. The novelty of the article lies in its focus on SME sustainability, which was measured across four dimensions: economic, environmental, social, and governance. Finally, the study's findings can help policymakers and enterprise managers apply research results to develop SMEs sustainability policies as follows:

1. Enhancing Strategic Flexibility (X1): Policymakers should encourage SMEs to promote long-term flexibility actively. Agile cultures with open communication and decentralised decision-making improve human capital, supply chain, information, and finance flexibility. This requires support from government or strategic partners through consulting, training, and advanced analytical tools to close capability gaps, apply best practices, and strengthen underdeveloped areas within the flexibility framework.
2. Promoting Proactive Adaptability (X2): Policymakers should encourage proactive investment in IoT and AI to improve production adaptability and customer responsiveness.

Thus, SMEs should be helped to use technology to improve efficiency, time management, innovation, and market response.

3. Building Collaborative Resilience (X3): Policymakers should promote networking among government agencies, universities, and supply chain partners to manage and accelerate.

4. Fostering Innovation-Oriented Leadership (X4): Policies should emphasise the development of leadership and management abilities among small and medium enterprises. This includes effective communication and networking, relationship and co-creation, mobilising resources, and the ability to articulate a leadership commitment and support for sustainability.

5. Empowering People-Driven Innovation (X5): Policymakers should encourage innovation, employee engagement, and cross-functional learning in SMEs to upskill. To improve SMEs managers should receive innovation management and sustainability training.

6. Prioritising a Holistic Sustainability Framework: Policymakers should prioritise SMEs' sustainability across all four dimensions. Economic sustainability can be promoted by enhancing profitability, reducing costs, and increasing sales. Social sustainability involves raising awareness, promoting corporate responsibility, and facilitating inter-organisational networks. Environmental sustainability requires encouraging eco-friendly production, resource efficiency, and waste minimisation, and Governance should prioritise inclusive participation from strategic partners, stakeholders, and employees, which is rooted in shared decision-making, accountability, trust, and transparency for long-term sustainability.

Limitations and future research: The authors acknowledge several limitations in this study that offer avenues for future research. Firstly, the study employed a non-probability quota sampling method. While this approach was practical for reaching a diverse sample of SMEs across different food processing sectors in Thailand within realistic constraints, it inherently limits the generalizability of the findings to the entire population of 3,808 SMEs. There is potential for selection bias, as the sample may not be perfectly representative. Therefore, future research could aim to replicate this study's model using a probability sampling technique, such as stratified random sampling, to validate these findings and enhance their external validity. Moreover, this study employed global frameworks to measure sustainability, although governance for small- and medium-sized SMEs is not yet fully incorporated. Thus, future research should investigate the feasibility of evaluating this model in medium-sized enterprises that possess the operational capacity to implement comprehensive sustainability practices encompassing economic, social, environmental, and governance dimensions. In light of the increasing importance of digital transformation and platform-based business models for SME competitiveness and global market integration, future research could investigate their potential as mediators or enhancers of the organisational agility and innovation impacts on sustainability.

Institutional Review Board Statement

The study was conducted according to the guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki, the Belmont report, CIOMS guidelines, and the principle of the international conference on harmonization-good clinical practice (ICH-GCP), and approved by the Research Ethics Review Committee for Research Involving Human Subjects: The Second Allied Academic Group in Social Sciences, Humanities, and Fine and Applied Arts at Chulalongkorn University with COA No. 529/67

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Appendix 1

Flexibility (X1)

OPERF1

Our business regularly evaluates opportunities and proactively adjusts operations accordingly.

OPERF2	Our business manages resources, processes, and delivery methods to respond to customer demands.
OPERF3	Our business adapts product design and customization to changing consumer needs.
OPERF4	Our business ensures consistent product quality aligned with international standards.
OPERF5	Our business provides responsive and timely customer service.
HUMANF1	Our business engages employees in decision-making to improve product quality, reduce costs, or enhance customer service.
HUMANF2	Our business promotes employee participation in expressing opinions and suggestions.
HUMANF3	Our business manages workforce equity, such as gender and age inclusion.
INFORF1	Our business continuously monitors customer needs and market trends.
INFORF2	Our business regularly analyzes information related to customers, competitors, and technologies to ensure data is up to date.
INFORF3	Our business evaluates marketing, production, and partnership strategies in response to environmental changes.
SCF1	Our business can adjust production quantities and delivery schedules to meet customer requirements.
SCF2	Our business can flexibly manage changes in supplier order quantities and delivery conditions.
SCF3	Our business is capable of shortening production lead times to ensure timely delivery.
SCF4	Our business analyzes supplier options to take advantage of cost reductions, improved quality, and optimal logistics channels.
FINANF1	Our business can easily access external sources of funding.
FINANF2	Our business maintains contingency financial plans in response to changing business conditions.
FINANF3	Our business consistently prepares accounting records and utilizes financial reports for informed decision-making.
Adaptability (X2)	
RESOURCE1	Our business adopts new technologies and innovations to improve operational efficiency.
RESOURCE2	Our business can allocate and reconfigure supply chain resources—such as raw material sourcing, distribution, and supplier selection—in alignment with current business conditions.
RESOURCE3	Our business allocates resources internally (e.g., investment in personnel, technologies, and production processes) to maximize value and respond effectively to evolving market demands.
OL1	Our business supports continuous employee development to equip them with new skills and knowledge in response to changing demands.
OL2	Our business actively seeks external collaborations and partnerships to enhance knowledge sharing.

- OL3 Our business emphasizes learning and capability development aligned with ongoing business operations.
- CMC1 Our business adapts business models (e.g., spin-offs, startups) to respond effectively to change.
- CMC2 Our business implements new techniques and work processes to stay aligned with evolving circumstances.
- CMC3 Our business can operate uninterrupted under various conditions due to having contingency plans in place.

Resilience (X3)

- LC1 Our business adjusts its strategies in response to changing environments.
- LC2 Our business applies digital technologies to enhance internal collaboration.
- LC3 Our business fosters a culture of boldness and risk-taking to support innovation and ensure business survival.
- NERWORK1 Our business builds networks with government agencies, private sector partners, and academic institutions to remain resilient in times of crisis.
- NERWORK2 Our business participates in trade exhibitions and seminars hosted by public and private organizations.
- NERWORK3 Our business establishes strong relationships within the supply chain and across functional departments to support long-term sustainability.
- CHAGER1 Our business maintains contingency plans to reduce production risk and prevent operational disruptions.
- CHAGER2 Our business has recovery protocols in place to manage crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic or technological changes.

Leadership (X4)

- LCS1 Our leadership actively promotes business innovation, such as developing products that deliver both economic and social value.
- LCS2 Our leadership allocates resources and provides incentives to support innovation and technology initiatives.
- LCS3 Our leadership consistently demonstrates support for innovative products or services.
- LCS4 Our leadership prioritizes innovation and aligns innovation planning with overall business goals and strategies.
- COM1 Our business fosters a collaborative and friendly work atmosphere that promotes teamwork.
- COM2 Our business receives support from public sector agencies to drive and enhance innovation initiatives.
- COM3 Our business integrates internal networks as part of innovation-related activities.
- RELA1 Our business emphasizes the exchange of information, knowledge, and insights with partner networks, supply chains, and customers to foster innovation.

RELA2	Our business builds strong relationships among the supply chain, organization, and customers to support co-creation in innovation processes.
RESOURCES1	Employees in our organization are capable of using digital tools and technologies effectively.
RESOURCES2	Our business leverages the unique resources of partner networks to empower employees in generating innovations.
People (X5)	
PAR1	Our leadership assesses each employee's needs and capabilities and promotes self-development that respects individual differences.
PAR2	Employees from different departments share their knowledge and expertise to drive innovation.
PAR3	Our business facilitates cross-functional meetings or collaborative projects to encourage ongoing teamwork and idea-sharing.
CI1	Our business emphasizes communication and coordination across departments or teams when implementing innovation initiatives.
CI2	Our business treats employees, management, and stakeholders fairly and with respect.
CI3	Our business fosters a culture of continuous learning that supports innovation and development.
TRAIN1	Our business provides ongoing training and development to enhance employees' innovation skills and capabilities.
TRAIN2	Our business encourages idea generation, experimentation, and learning to improve efficiency and create business value.
TRAIN3	Our business prioritizes cultivating a learning culture among employees to enable innovation.
MOTIVA1	Our business recognizes and rewards individuals or teams for innovative thinking.
MOTIVA2	Our business encourages and motivates employees to develop creative solutions and generate new insights.
Organizational Sustainability (Y)	
T_FINGROETH	How would you rate your business's financial returns?
T_MARKETCOMPET	How would you assess your business's competitiveness in the market?
T_CUSTOMER	How would you rate the outcomes of customer satisfaction and customer behavior toward your business?
T_EMPLOYEE	How would you rate employee satisfaction and motivation within your business?
T_COMMUNITY	To what extent does your business strategically support, develop, and generate a positive impact on the community?
T_ENERGY	How would you rate your business's environmental strategies in sustainable energy use, resource management, and monitoring environmental performance?
T_MATERIALS	To what extent does your business practice environmentally friendly material management (e.g., sustainable, biodegradable, or green materials) to enhance organizational sustainability?

- T_PARTICIPATION How would you rate the strategic participation of employees, stakeholders, and partners in decision-making, with emphasis on transparency, trust, and long-term sustainability?
- T_ACCURACY To what extent does your business operate in alignment with laws, ethics, and transparency, including systems for grievance handling and responsible governance?
- T_TRANSPARENCY How would you rate your business's transparency in information disclosure, access rights, and systematic data verification?
- T_RESPON To what extent does your business demonstrate social responsibility across operations, employee care, and management of social and environmental risks?

Source: Authors' (2025)